

Boosting phylogenetic bootstrap with structural information

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Abstract

The growing influx of genomic data is putting strong pressure on the improvement of phylogeny reconstruction methods. In a phylogeny, trustworthy reliability branch support estimates are as important as the tree itself. In this study, we show that reliability support values based on bootstrapping can be improved by combining protein sequence and structural information. Our approach relies on the systematic comparison of homologous

intra-molecular structural distances. We show that these variations support the computation of tree-like distance matrices that can be resolved into phylogenetic trees using distance-based methods. These trees lend themselves to the estimate of bootstrap support values. They bear strong similarities to their sequence-based counterparts but are sufficiently distinct so that their information content may be combined. Using a downsampling strategy we show that these new combined bootstrap support values yield improved discrimination between correct and incorrect branches. Our approach, named multistrap, is suitable for both predicted and experimental 3D structures.

Introduction

The resilience of protein folds is well established and has routinely been used to infer homology across evolutionary timespans incompatible with sequence analysis (Chothia and Lesk, 1986; Rost, 1999; Illergård *et al.*, 2009). This observation has led to the speculation that the quantitative comparison of protein folds could be used as a metric to resolve deep nodes in phylogenetic trees (Johnson, Sutcliffe, *et al.*, 1990; Longo *et al.*, 2020; Malik *et al.*, 2020).

The Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) is commonly used to compare protein folds. RMSD measures require a rigid superposition of the considered structures (Johnson, Sutcliffe, *et al.*, 1990; Johnson, Šali, *et al.*, 1990). The Template Modeling Score (TM-Score) (Zhang and Skolnick, 2004) is a normalized variation of the original RMSD, which is now routinely used when comparing alternative superpositions across structures of different lengths. The TM-Score does not, however, correct the RMSD's high sensitivity to conformation changes (Rabiller *et al.*, 2010).

An obvious alternative to measuring global fold superpositions is the systematic comparison of all homologous intra-molecular distances (IMD). Several IMD-based comparison methods have been reported that do not require a superposition and are therefore less sensitive than RMSD to conformational variations. The first such method was the distance RMSD (dRMSD) (Levitt, 1976). Similar measures were later shown to be suitable for the identification of distantly related structural homologs (Holm and Sander, 1993; Holm *et al.*, 2006). IMD comparisons were also used to quantify multiple

sequence alignment (MSA) structural accuracy (O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2004; Armougom *et al.*, 2006). The Local Distance Difference Test (IDDT) score is the most recent IMD based method. It leverages IMDs to assess the concordance of local structural features between two protein structures within specified regions, thus offering a detailed assessment of local similarity (Mariani *et al.*, 2013). The IDDT has been extensively used to assess prediction accuracy in the last two CASP (Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction) challenges. In their original report, the authors (Mariani *et al.*, 2013) used simulated data to demonstrate the increased robustness of IMD metrics over their RMSD-based counterparts when dealing with alternative conformations of the same protein.

IMD-based metrics bear numerical properties sufficiently similar to sequence-based distances so that they can be used to resolve phylogenetic trees using standard distance-based phylogenetic methods such as Neighbour Joining (Saitou and Nei, 1987), or Minimum Evolution tree reconstruction methods (ME) (Lefort *et al.*, 2015). In this study, we explored the potential of intra-molecular distances to be treated as evolutionary characters and set out to ask if these characters could either help the reconstruction of phylogenetic trees or provide new ways of estimating branch reliability.

The use of structures for phylogeny reconstruction remains limited by the lack of independent objective reference datasets that would allow unambiguously establishing the accuracy of a phylogeny based on structural comparisons. Consequently, rather than trying to quantify the relative merits of various alternative phylogeny reconstruction methods, we focused our efforts on measuring the agreement between structure-based

and sequence-based phylogenies in a controlled environment. We did so by systematically exploring the relationship between distance-based methods, using sequences or structures, and Maximum Likelihood (ML) reconstruction methods, which are generally considered, along with bayesian methods, to deliver the most accurate phylogenies (Felsenstein, 1985, 2003; Guindon and Gascuel, 2003; Alfaro, 2003; Yang, 2014). Our results show a significant level of congruence between sequence and structure-based phylogenetic reconstructions. We took advantage of this property to design a hybrid bootstrap support method named multistrap, which combines sequence and structural information. Using a downsampling strategy we found this hybrid support able to better discriminate between correct and incorrect branches than similar methods based on sequence or structure alone.

Results

The IMD metric achieves high tree-likeness. An essential property of evolutionary characters is their capacity to reflect the true distance between two taxa in such a way that the distance directly measured on a pair of taxa (input distance) is as close as possible to the one recovered from the tree by summing the lengths of the branches separating these two taxa (patristic distance). This property is named tree-likeness and can be quantified by measuring the coefficient of determination (R^2) between the input and patristic distances. To assess the suitability of the IMDs as evolutionary characters, we first estimated the IMD metric's tree-likeness and compared it with two alternative metrics: the TM-Score (TM), and the minimum evolution approach based on sequence comparisons (ME) implemented in FastME (LG+G model) (Lefort *et al.*, 2015), a well-

established software for distance-based phylogeny reconstruction. To carry out this comparison we assembled a reference benchmark featuring 508 datasets, each made from 10 to 133 homologous protein sequences with known experimental 3D structures. These datasets were obtained by collecting all the experimental PDBs associated with PFAM domain families (see methods). We estimated an MSA on each dataset using mTM-align, the best-performing multiple sequence aligner on this benchmark (Supplementary Fig. S1). For each resulting MSA, we then computed three input distance matrices using the IMD, TM, and ME metrics. We used these distance matrices to construct the corresponding phylogenetic trees using FastME, from which we subsequently derived patristic distance matrices. We then measured the coefficients of determination between input and patristic distances on each dataset and compared the median values. Overall, the two structure-based metrics slightly outperform the sequence-based metric (median R^2 of 0.970 for the IMD, 0.962 for the TM and 0.898 for ME trees, one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test all p-values $< 2.2e-16$) (Fig. 1, Table 1). We obtained comparable results when repeating the analysis using four different MSA protocols entirely based on structures (3D-Coffee, trimmed and untrimmed) or sequences (T-Coffee, trimmed and untrimmed) (Supplementary Fig. S2, Supplementary Tables 1,2). These results show that distance matrices estimated from structures contain a signal compatible with the resolution of a phylogenetic tree. This property is important and necessary for any distance-based evolutionary character but it does not imply the correctness of the inferred trees.

Comparison of IMD and TM phylogenetic tree topologies. The above analyses stop short of quantifying the relative phylogenetic accuracies of IMD and TM trees. We addressed this issue by comparing the agreement of IMD and TM trees with their Maximum Likelihood counterparts (ML based on sequences) using the Robinson-Foulds (RF) (Robinson and Foulds, 1981) topological distance (Fig. 2). Overall, we found that the IMD and TM trees had equal levels of topological agreement with their ML references in 156 out of 508 datasets, while they differed in the 352 remaining datasets. Among these 352 datasets, the IMD trees were the ones having the best agreement with the ML references (199 and 153, respectively, sign test p -value=0.008). These results are consistent with the observation that IMD and ML trees yield a higher level of topological agreement than that measured between TM and ML trees (average normalized topological RF distance = 0.42 and 0.40 respectively) (Table 1).

Sequence and structural bootstrap support values agree strongly on highly supported branches. Phylogenetic tree topologies are only considered conclusive when complemented with branch support values – commonly estimated by Felsenstein bootstrap support (Felsenstein, 1985). We implemented the IMD method in such a way that the columns can be sampled with replacement and used to generate bootstrap replicates suitable for a standard Felsenstein bootstrap procedure. As expected, we found IMD bootstrap support values to be in broad agreement with similar support measurements computed on ML or ME trees ($R=0.77$ between IMD and ML, $R=0.72$ between IMD and ME) (Fig. 3A-B, Supplementary Fig. S3-4). We also found a strong correlation between the average IMD bootstrap support values of individual trees and the

fraction of branches they share with ME or ML trees ($R=0.67$ for both IMD vs ME and IMD vs ML). The topological agreement is especially strong when considering branches with high support values (Fig. 3C-D). On average, the IMD and the ML trees share 42.1% of their branches. Yet, when considering the most extreme case, i.e. IMD branches with bootstrap support values equal to 100, this agreement reaches 83.17% (1,591 branches in total) (Table 1). We achieved similar results when comparing the IMD and the ME trees (Supplementary Fig. S5-6). Altogether these results further strengthen our observation that the variations of intra-molecular distances capture aspects of protein evolution relevant to phylogenetic reconstruction. Bootstrap support values are, however, generally higher on the IMD trees (43.47 and 66.37% for ME and IMD trees, respectively). These values should not be interpreted as suggesting a higher reliability for the underlying topologies, but rather as a consequence of the high level of redundancy in the structural information, obviously constrained by the 3D models they are collected from.

Structural variations carry denser evolutionary content than sequences. The lack of established reference datasets makes it difficult to objectively determine if the structure-based trees are as informative or even more than their sequence-based counterparts. As an alternative to a reference-based analysis, we designed a controlled titration of the relative evolutionary information content within structures and sequences. Titration was achieved through a downsampling procedure. We first collected the 56 datasets (out of 508) featuring at least 200 nearly ungapped columns (less than 5% gaps in their mTM-align MSA). For each dataset, we sampled without replacement a sub-MSA of exactly 200 nearly ungapped columns, estimated the corresponding trees (IMD, ME,

ML), and collected the shared branches to be used as a reference. The average fraction of shared branches across all branches is 0.44. Each dataset was then progressively downsampled by removing columns five by five down to a minimum of ten columns. At each point, the trees were re-estimated and re-evaluated for the fraction of recapitulated reference branches. The complete procedure (i.e. starting from the sampling of 200 columns in each of the 56 datasets) was repeated ten times and the resulting data was combined into a single titration graph (Fig. 4A, Supplementary Fig. S7). When using ten columns only, the IMD trees recapitulate about 60% of the reference branches in contrast to 44% and 42% for the ML and ME trees, respectively. The trend of a higher reference branch recapitulation in titrated IMD trees is robust and remains unaltered across the full titration (Table 2). These observations support the usability of structural information when estimating phylogenies and also indicate that the information content within intramolecular distances is overall similar to the one available in sequences, albeit slightly denser.

Multiple bootstrap methods provide a means to complement sequence data with structural information. The lack of an objective independent criterion to determine the relative merits of our tree reconstruction methods led us to explore the suitability of combining alternative bootstrap support values. We named this approach multistrap. Multistrap starts by generating bootstrap replicates separately using different tree methods. These replicates are then combined using the arithmetic mean to estimate the final bootstrap support values of each branch on a target tree. We benchmarked multistrap on the titration dataset. The broad strategy involved defining reference

branches on the complete datasets (i.e. non-downsampled), measuring bootstrap support values on the downsampled datasets, and evaluating the capacity of the various combinations of these bootstrap support values to discriminate between reference and non-reference branches on the complete datasets.

In practice, we first estimated IMD, ME, and ML trees with 100 bootstrap replicates on the 56 non-downsampled datasets (200 columns). We used these trees to define sets of reference branches using all possible combinations with a cutoff of 80% support (e.g. branches supported in 80% or more of the IMD replicates, hereafter referred to as IMD80; branches supported by 80% or more of the IMD replicates AND the ME replicates, hereafter referred to as IMD80∩ME80 etc...). These combinations provided us with seven sets of reference branches containing between 37.8% (IMD80) and 24.9% (IMD80∩ME80∩ML80) of the 829 internal branches occurring in the ML trees (Supplementary Table 3). Since these sets and associated trees are designed for a discriminative analysis, we removed datasets featuring only reference branches (or none). This left us with 52 to 55 usable datasets per reference branch set.

Given these reference branches, we set out to estimate the branch support values we wanted to test. To that effect, we computed new IMD, ME, and ML bootstrap replicate trees using 25 columns only and used these downsampled replicates to re-estimate the branch supports in the initial ML trees (i.e. ML trees based on 200 columns had their branch supports re-estimated using replicates based on 25 columns). Given the bootstrap support values computed for each branch and the labels provided by one of the seven

reference sets, it is possible to evaluate the discriminative capacity of the bootstrap method using a receiving operator characteristic area under the curve (ROC AUC). The AUC is equal to 1 if the bootstrap support values perfectly separate the references from the rest, or equal to 0.5 if the discrimination is random. The downsampled bootstrap support values were combined by averaging the alternative supports of a given branch given any bootstrap method combination (e.g. ML, IMD+ML, IMD+ML+ME, etc.). We did an exhaustive all-against-all analysis in which all possible definitions of reference branches were analyzed using all possible combinations of downsampled bootstrap support values (Table 3).

This table, which spans the entire combinatorial space, is well-suited to quantify the added value associated with any specific bootstrap method. For instance, when considering the ML80 line (i.e. reference branches defined using ML non-downsampled replicates), one can see that the discriminative capacity of the ML+IMD bootstrap support values (ML+IMD column) is superior to the one measured by ML only (0.880 and 0.843 respectively). Since on this line, the reference branches definition does not rely on any IMD data, one can then conclude that the IMD bootstrap support values' contribution entirely accounts for the observed difference. On this same line, similar reasoning can be applied when comparing the ME+IMD column with ME alone (0.858 and 0.794 respectively) or the ME+ML+IMD column with ME+ML (0.868 and 0.832 respectively). Overall, when considering all similar matched pairs of values based on reference branches derived independently from IMD (i.e. ME80, ML80, ME80nML80 lines) we systematically found a net gain associated with the addition of IMD to the bootstrap

protocol. As one would expect, the results are even more pronounced when considering experiments in which the reference branches definition includes IMD information (IMD80, IMD80∩ME80, IMD80∩ML80, IMD80∩ME80∩ML80). A systematic comparison of the possible combinations shows that the differences between +/-IMD columns are all significant (Supplementary Table 4). Very similar results were obtained when basing the analysis on ME trees rather than ML trees (Supplementary Table 5) or when using alternative ways of combining the downsampled bootstrap support values such as geometric mean, minimum, or maximum (Supplementary Table 6).

The AUC analysis supports the usefulness of combining sequence and structure-based bootstrap replicates but it does not indicate whether sensible general bootstrap support value thresholds exist that could be systematically applied to new datasets. We addressed this question by estimating for each dataset and each reference/bootstrap combination the bootstrap support value threshold providing an optimal separation between reference and non-reference branches. We defined the optimal threshold as the one yielding the highest possible Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) and therefore providing a good compromise between the fraction of true negative (sensitivity) and the fraction of true positive (specificity). The results (Supplementary Table 7) indicate that in the three reference branch sets derived without IMD information (ML80, ME80, ME80∩ML80), the inclusion of IMD structural information predominantly results in increased sensitivity and specificity. When adding IMD information we also observed an increase in the optimal bootstrap support value thresholds of 3 to 5 percent points. This increase is consistent with the higher numerical values observed on the IMD supports but

cannot be directly interpreted as an improvement. We also observed that the optimal average bootstrap support values are associated with relatively high standard deviations (Supplementary Table 8) that suggest a large dispersion. Interestingly, the standard deviations were 3 to 6 percent points lower when considering IMD-based combinations, a decreased dispersion consistent with the notion that structural information contributes towards increased robustness of bootstrap reliability estimates.

Beyond experimental protein structures. At the time this manuscript is being written, the PDB contains about 210,000 experimentally determined protein structures – merely a fraction of the 250 million protein sequences contained in UniProt. In such a context, the relevance of structural information when estimating phylogenies may be considered purely anecdotal. The recent report of highly accurate methods for protein structure prediction (Jumper *et al.*, 2021) is, however, dramatically changing this situation and prompted us to explore the suitability of AlphaFold2 (AF2) models when doing IMD-based phylogenetic reconstructions. We, therefore, collected the available predicted 3D structures from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (Varadi *et al.*, 2022) for the sequences used in the titration and reproduced the entire analysis using these models, including the MSA step. The results achieved on AF2 models were very similar to those measured on experimental structures, albeit slightly superior (Fig. 4B). This important observation suggests that there may be significant merits in systematically combining AF2 modeling information with sequence data when estimating phylogenetic tree reliability.

Conclusion - Discussion

The notion that structural variation could inform phylogenetic inference has long been intriguing and sometimes divisive to the scientific community (Johnson, Sutcliffe, *et al.*, 1990; Malik *et al.*, 2020). On the one hand, fold resilience is expected to provide insights into the deepest branches of the tree of life, with some of the most ancient folds spanning billions of years of evolutionary history (Gruic-Sovulj *et al.*, 2022), but on the other hand, this same resilience may lead to high levels of purifying selections and act as a confounding factor, as shown for instance in the reconstruction of ancient viral lineages (Wertheim and Kosakovsky Pond, 2011). On top of this, the very high pressure of selection under which protein folds evolve can induce convergent evolution processes, another major confounding factor in phylogenetic tree reconstruction. At the level of complete protein folds, this issue remains disputed with diverging and converging hypotheses co-existing to account for the emergence of ancient structural motifs, like the $\alpha\beta$ sandwich (Longo *et al.*, 2020). Yet, locally convergent evolutionary processes are more widely accepted and documented, especially in regions evolving under strong purifying selection like enzymatic active sites (Holliday *et al.*, 2005). Despite its confounding nature, convergent evolution is not specific to structures and can equally impair sequence-based phylogeny reconstruction (Castoe *et al.*, 2009).

While convergent evolution may occur both on structures and sequences, the issue of conformational changes is specific to structures and represents yet another challenge for structure-based phylogeny. For instance, most protein kinase domains can be found in a closed or open form (Rabiller *et al.*, 2010), a variation that can dominate a naive structural

classification if left uncorrected. In this context, one can intuitively understand why IMD methods should be less affected by conformational variations, than RMSD approaches. Indeed, whenever they occur, conformational variations will only affect a subset of the internal distances but will lead to spurious averaged rigid superpositions that will affect all the distances measured by an RMSD. This hypothesis was thoroughly tested in the validation of the IDDT metric where the authors used extensive simulations to demonstrate the IDDT capacity to recover the domain-based structural similarities even when applied globally on multi-domain proteins in different conformations. In this same study, the authors were able to show the superiority of their IMD-based approach over the Global Distance Test used in previous CASP contests and based on rigid superpositions. Our observation of slightly better performances when using IMD rather than TM-based trees supports this observation.

In this work we show that phylogenetic trees based on the comparison of internal distances display many of the desirable properties of high-accuracy phylogenetic trees: they have a high explained variance, and their highly supported branches are in strong agreement with maximum likelihood analysis. Unfortunately, the lack of gold standards reference phylogenetic trees makes it impossible to objectively compare the relative merits of these methods. We did, however, develop a controlled set-up that allowed us to unambiguously establish that sequences and structures contain similar amounts of evolutionary signals and that these signals can effectively be combined to yield improved branch support estimates.

The timing of our report is especially relevant as the biological data landscape is undergoing unprecedented changes. Thanks to AF2 (Jumper *et al.*, 2021) and linguistic models (Lin *et al.*, 2023) the prospect of collecting trustworthy high-resolution structures for each and every known protein is now realistic. At the same time, a massive effort is underway to sequence the genomes of all existing species (Lewin *et al.*, 2022). This wealth of data will make it possible to explore very large homologous datasets in which the systematic estimation of gene tree topologies should cast a new light on the emergence of the most basic molecular functions. This scaled-up genomics will require unprecedented amounts of data integration. With models spanning millions of genomes and billions of homologous sequences, we anticipate reliability assessment to become a major bottleneck. Multistrap addresses this precise issue by providing a simple and effective solution.

Methods

Multiple Sequence Alignment Methods computation, trimming, and evaluation.

Multiple sequence alignments were computed using T-Coffee (v13.45.60.cd84d2a) (Notredame *et al.*, 2000) with default parameters. The structure-based multiple sequence alignments were computed using either mTM-align (v20180725) (Dong *et al.*, 2018) or 3D-Coffee (O'Sullivan *et al.*, 2004) using the `-method=sap_pair, TMalign_pair` option. The trimmed alignments were produced using the `automated1` option of TrimAl (Capella-Gutiérrez *et al.*, 2009). After evaluating the MSAs for their structure-based accuracy using the NiRMSD option of the T-Coffee package (Supplementary Fig. S1) we selected mTM-align as the default structural aligner for the main analysis.

Reference benchmark dataset. A total of 508 datasets featuring homologous protein sequences with experimental X-ray structures (Burley *et al.*, 2017) were assembled using PFAM (v28.0; (Finn *et al.*, 2016)). The datasets were constructed so as to feature at least ten sequences and be successfully alignable (i.e. no computational abortion) by the three considered multiple aligners (T-Coffee, 3D-Coffee, mTM-align). The datasets contain between 10 and 133 sequences, with an average of 21 sequences per dataset for a total of 10,258 distinct structural segments. The average pairwise identity, as estimated on the T-Coffee MSAs, is 32%. The full dataset is available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447443>).

Sequence-based distance matrix. Pairwise distances were estimated from the mTM-align MSAs using the LG model of FastME with a gamma shape parameter of 1 (Le and Gascuel, 2008).

TM-score. Given a pair of sequences A and B, the TM-Score is computed by mTM-align using the formula

$$TM\text{-score}(A, B) = \max \left[\frac{1}{L_S} \sum_{i=1}^{L_C} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{d_i}{d_0}\right)^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where L_S is the sequence length of the smallest structure, L_C the number of considered ungapped columns in the sequence alignment of A and B, d_i the structural distance between the two α -carbons of residues in i^{th} considered column and d_0 a normalization

constant set to 0.5 for sequences shorter than or equal to 21 amino-acids or otherwise according to:

$$d_0 = 1.24(L_S - 15)^{1/3} - 1.8 \quad (2)$$

Intra-molecular distance-based metric. The IMD metric aggregates the differences of intra-molecular distances measured across pairs of homologous sites provided in the form of an MSA (i.e. pair of columns). Given the pairwise projection of two sequences A and B from an MSA and given all the possible pairs of column x and y, with D_A^{xy} being the distance between the α -carbons of the residues in column x and y of sequence A in Angström, the IMD metric is defined as follows:

$$IMD(A, B) = \frac{\sum_{x,y} |D_A^{xy} - D_B^{xy}|}{\text{number of pairs}(x,y)} \quad (3)$$

Phylogenetic tree reconstruction and comparisons. The sequence-based ME trees (ME) were generated using FastME (v2.1.6.4, download instructions: https://github.com/lmansouri/Phylo-IMD/blob/main/Dockerfiles/fastme_dockerfile) with the following command (Lefort *et al.*, 2015):

```
fastme -i <alignment> -o <output filename> -m BioNJ -p LG -g 1.0 -s -n -z 5 -b 100 -B <replicates filename> -O <output distance matrix filename>
```

The structure-based trees (TM and IMD) were generated using FastME with the TM - or IMD-based distance matrix:

```
fastme -i <distance matrix> -s -n -z 5
```

The sequence-based maximum likelihood trees (ML) were estimated using iQtree (Nguyen *et al.*, 2015):

```
iqtree -s <alignment> -b 100
```

Tree comparisons. Topological comparisons between pairs of trees were carried out using the *phangorn* package (Schliep, 2011) implementation of the Robinson–Foulds (RF) distance measure (Robinson and Foulds, 1981):

```
RF.dist(<tree1> ,<tree2>, normalize=T)
```

IMD bootstrap replicates. The IMD metric is implemented in the T-Coffee package (Notredame *et al.*, 2000). The following command line generates a distance matrix useable by FastME:

```
export THREED_TREE_MODE=10
t_coffee -other_pg seq_reformat -in <alignment file> -in2 <t_coffee template file> -
action +replicates <number of bootstrap replicates, 100 in our case> +phylo3d
+print_replicates -output dm
```

Here, the template file declares the PDB files associated with each sequence as follows:

```
><name of the sequence in the alignment file> _P_ <PDB structure file>
```

This procedure supports the generation of both the complete distance matrix (first output matrix) and a total of 100 bootstrap replicates, each generated by randomly drawing first a set of N columns with replacement and then drawing with replacement a set of N^2 pairs of columns among the N columns previously drawn. This two-step procedure makes it possible to avoid systematically sampling all possible pairs, as would happen if the N^2 pairs were directly sampled from the original MSA. The replicates can be fed to any

distance-based tree method, like FastME, so as to generate Felsenstein-like bootstrap branch support values.

The replicate trees were generated with the command:

```
fastme -i <distance matrix> -g 1.0 -s -n -z 5
```

The replicate trees were then concatenated and the support values for each branch were calculated using the function *prop.clades()* in the phangorn package (Schliep, 2011).

Titration. The full benchmark dataset was first filtered to retain datasets featuring at least 200 columns, each containing a gap in less than 5% of the sequences. This filtering returned 56 datasets, which were used to generate replicates. In each dataset, 200 columns were randomly drawn without replacement, the resulting MSA was used to estimate ML, ME, and IMD trees. The branches common to all three trees were then collected and used as a reference. The procedure was repeated ten times, thus generating a total of 560 datasets containing 3,371 reference branches in total (40.3% of the 8,361 branches in the entire dataset). The titration was done by gradual downsampling, five columns at a time. At each downsampling step, the trees were estimated (ML, ME and IMD) and evaluated for the fraction of reference branches they contained.

Titration on AlphaFold2 (AF2) predicted structures. Protein structures were collected for the 56 datasets of the titration dataset from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database v4 with the "get_structures" pipeline, accessible at https://github.com/luisas/get_structures/tree/phyloimd with the command

```
nextflow run main.nf -profile phylo3d
```

The database search was set up with foldseek version c7e4a37856b49438eae03bbfcdf1588cbce0695 with the command

```
"foldseek databases afdB AlphaFold/UniProt afdB tmp"
```

Then, for every collected sequence, mmseqs (v14.7e284) was used to search for structures that meet two criteria: full coverage of the query protein sequence and a minimum amino acid sequence identity of 99%. In total, we managed to collect all the AF2 structures in 49 out of the 56 initial datasets.

Multistrap ROC curve and MCC analysis. An ML tree was estimated on one non-downsampled TAlign MSA (200 columns) for each of the 56 datasets used in the titration. Three sets of 100 bootstrap replicate trees were then computed on these same MSAs using IMD, ME and ML. These bootstrap collections were used to estimate three support values for each ML tree branch (i.e. IMD, ME, and ML), and the combination of these values was used to define seven distinct sets of reference branches. These sets were estimated by combining the bootstrap support values in all possible ways and by keeping branches having support values superior or equal to 80% (i.e. IMD80, ME80, ML80, ME80∩IMD80, ML80∩IMD80, ME80∩ML80, ME80∩ML80∩IMD80). Three new bootstrap collections (IMD, ME, and ML) were then estimated on the downsampled TAlign MSAs (25 columns). These three collections were used to estimate three branch support bootstrap values for every branch of the initial ML trees (i.e. the trees based on 200 columns). A total of seven sets of multistrap branch support values were then

produced by combining the collection support values in all possible ways (IMD, ME, ML, ME+IMD, ML+IMD, ME+ML, ME+ML+IMD). In each set, the multistrap values were defined as the arithmetic mean of the combined values. A ROC AUC analysis (R pROC library) was then carried out on each possible reference branches set/multistrap set (49 pairs in total) to quantify the capacity of the multistrap support values to discriminate between reference and non-reference branches. The AUCs were computed individually on every dataset and eventually averaged to yield the tabulated readouts. An optimal MCC analysis was carried out on the same data and used to identify the multistrap bootstrap support value thresholds yielding the highest MCCs on each dataset of each possible branch support/multistrap combination. The corresponding values were collected along with their associated thresholds, sensitivities (TP/TP+FN), and specificities (TN/TN+FN). The entire analysis was also done using ME trees instead of ML trees in the first step. Three other protocols were tested for the multistrap combination: geometric mean, and minimum, or maximum of the combined values.

Reproducing the multistrap analysis

The multistrap analysis presented here can be automatically deployed using the multistrap profile of the Phylo-IMD pipeline (<https://github.com/l-mansouri/Phylo-IMD>) with the command line:

```
`nextflow run main.nf -profile multistrap -fasta <id.fasta> -templates <id.template> -pdbs <id.seq1.pdb, id.seq2.pdb .. >`
```

The whole procedure is extensively documented along with input files and example input datasets on: <https://github.com/l-mansouri/Phylo-IMD/blob/main/README.md>.

Multistrap is also available as a standalone executable within the T-Coffee package:

<https://www.tcoffee.org>.

Computation. Computation was carried out on a cluster running Scientific Linux release 7.2. The alignments and the phylogenetic reconstructions were run within separate containers based on the Debian GNU/Linux operating system

Data Availability

The reference benchmark dataset (see Methods) was deposited in Zenodo under <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447443>.

Code Availability

The pipeline was implemented in Nextflow (Di Tommaso *et al.*, 2017) and was run using Singularity containers. The code is available at: <https://github.com/l-mansouri/Phylo-IMD>.

TABLES

	Median R^2 (input, patristic)	Average BS	Congruence with ML trees	Congruence with ML trees (BS>=75)	ML Shared branches (count)	BS=100 ML Shared branches (count)
ME	0.898	43.47	0.67	0.87	67.00% (5,601)	100% (552)
TM	0.962		0.40		39.75% (3,240)	
IMD	0.970	66.37	0.42	0.55	42.11% (3,416)	83.17% (1,591)

Table 1: Summary statistics of ME, TM and IMD trees. R^2 is the coefficient of determination computed between the input and the patristic distances; *Average BS* is the average bootstrap support values measured on the corresponding trees. Supports are in a 0-100 range with high values indicating high support. *Congruence with ML trees* is the average normalized topological agreement (1-normalized RF) between the tree and the ML reference (low values indicate high agreement); *Congruence with ML trees (BS>=75)* reports the average agreement measure restricted to trees having an average bootstrap support value superior or equal to 75. *ML shared branches* indicates the unweighted average percentage of branches each tree set shares with ML trees. Absolute counts summed over all considered trees are indicated in parentheses. *BS=100 ML shared branches*: same as ML shared branches but restricted to branches having maximum support in each tree set. Absolute counts are indicated in parentheses.

Fraction of recapitulated reference branches after downsampling			
Tree Method	60%	75%	90%
ME	25 col.	50 col.	115 col.
ML	25 col.	55 col.	125 col.
IMD	10 col.	20 col.	70 col.

Table 2: Reference branch recapitulation after downsampling. The table reports the number of columns (col.) out of 200 required for the recapitulation of 60, 75, and 90% of the reference branches by each type of tree reconstruction method.

	Bootstrap combinations and resulting average AUC values							
Ref. branches	IMD	ME	ME +IMD	ML	ML +IMD	ME+ML	ME+ML +IMD	Number of datasets
IMD80	0.940 ± 0.06	0.783 ± 0.16	0.923 ± 0.07	0.794 ± 0.16	0.923 ± 0.08	0.796 ± 0.15	0.906 ± 0.09	55
ME80	0.810 ± 0.16	0.830 ± 0.14	0.860 ± 0.14	0.867 ± 0.11	0.873 ± 0.13	0.852 ± 0.13	0.869 ± 0.13	55
ME80nIMD80	0.910 ± 0.10	0.849 ± 0.12	0.922 ± 0.10	0.870 ± 0.13	0.926 ± 0.10	0.863 ± 0.13	0.915 ± 0.10	55
ML80	0.829 ± 0.15	0.794 ± 0.14	0.858 ± 0.14	0.843 ± 0.14	0.880 ± 0.13	0.832 ± 0.14	0.868 ± 0.13	54
ML80nIMD80	0.926 ± 0.09	0.822 ± 0.14	0.929 ± 0.07	0.848 ± 0.14	0.939 ± 0.07	0.841 ± 0.14	0.918 ± 0.08	52
ME80nML80	0.833 ± 0.14	0.842 ± 0.12	0.880 ± 0.11	0.882 ± 0.10	0.902 ± 0.09	0.869 ± 0.11	0.892 ± 0.09	55
ME80nML80nIMD80	0.911 ± 0.11	0.856 ± 0.13	0.929 ± 0.10	0.874 ± 0.13	0.934 ± 0.10	0.867 ± 0.14	0.923 ± 0.10	52
Average	0.880	0.825	0.900	0.854	0.911	0.846	0.899	

Table 3: Discrimination capacities of the downsampled bootstrap support values.

The table reports the average AUC measured on the titration family along with their standard deviation (\pm). *Ref. Branches* indicate which combination of non-downsampled bootstrap support values (as estimated on 200 columns) were used to select the reference branches as branches having a support of 80 or more among the replicates of the considered methods. *Bootstrap Combination* indicates which bootstrap replicates (estimated on 25 columns) were combined (arithmetic mean) to estimate the bootstrap

support values. The average AUC values indicate the discriminative capacity of the bootstrap combination between reference and non-reference branches as estimated on the original ML trees. Readouts in bold indicate bootstrap combinations featuring IMD. The shading indicates matched pairs of columns with and without IMD information (except for the first column). *Number of Datasets* indicates the number of discriminative datasets featuring both reference and non-reference branches that were used for the AUC analysis.

Fig. 1: Agreement between input and patristic distances. Distribution of the coefficient of determination (R^2) measured between the input and patristic distance matrices estimated on each dataset by ME (purple), TM (green), and IMD (blue). Boxplots show the median (0.898 for ME, 0.962 for TM, and 0.970 for IMD), quartiles (25th and 75th percentiles) and whiskers extend to 1.5 times the IQR.

Fig. 2: Comparison of the Robinson-Foulds (RF) measure of structure-based trees to the sequence-based reference (ML). The topological differences of each of the IMD-based trees (x-axis) and TM-score-based trees (y-axis) with the corresponding ML trees were compared. The figure in the top left corner (199) indicates the number of datasets for which the IMD topologies are more similar to the ML reference than the corresponding TM topology. The figure in the bottom right corner (153) indicates the opposite situation, and the figure in the main diagonal indicates datasets whose IMD and TM topologies are equally different to their ML references. The difference between the top and bottom figures is significant (sign test, p-value = 0.008).

Fig. 3: Relationship between bootstrap support value and topological similarities across tree methods. (A) For each dataset, the average bootstrap support value of the ME tree (y-axis) is plotted against its IMD counterpart (x-axis) and colored by the RF topological distance ($R=0.72$). The black overlaying line shows the running average RF (x-tree, y-tree, window size of 10) computed over the datasets sorted by IMD bootstrap

support values ($R=-0.67$). **(B)** represents a similar analysis with ML ($R=0.77$, $R=-0.67$). **(C)** The red line represents the fraction of branches that have an IMD bootstrap support value $\geq X$ (x-axis) and occur in the ME trees (all datasets put together). The blue line indicates which fraction of the total number of IMD branches (8,813 branches in total) are represented by each red point. **(D)** represents a similar analysis using ML trees as a reference.

Fig. 4: Information content comparison by titration. (A) Fraction of reference branches recovered on downsampled MSAs. The x-axis indicates the number of columns (out of a maximum of 200) kept in MSAs downsampled from 560 different MSAs (56 datasets sampled ten times each). The y-axis indicates the fraction of reference branches recovered. The envelope is the standard deviation. The gray dashed line indicates the number of columns required to recover 75% of the reference branches. **(B)** Represents a similar analysis carried out using the 49 datasets and their 490 MSA samples for which AlphaFold 2 predicted models could be obtained from the AF2 database.

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Author contributions

L.M., A.B., C.N. and O.G. designed the analysis, A.B. and L.M. carried out the validation, L.S. helped with the predicted structures retrieval and handling, and all the authors designed the validation procedure and L.M., A.B., C.N., L.S., B.L. and O.G. wrote the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.